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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes a verification and validation report for the MegaRoller WEC numerical model developed under WP1, describing the approach and the results of the comparison of the numerical model with already validated tools and experimental measurements. The numerical models were developed in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) and was documented in [D1.1, 2018] and [D1.2, 2019].

In [D1.1, 2018], a preliminary validation of the model was conducted using data from small-scale models which were tested in a wave tank at Queen's University in Belfast, UK. The present document builds on this preliminary validation exercise using real sea measurement data from the WaveRoller demonstration unit deployed at the Peniche site (Portugal). The following high-level conclusions can be drawn from the loads model validation exercise and sensitivity studies presented in this report:

- The PTO torque is relatively insensitive to the viscous drag formulation, PTO force cap and consideration of non-linear effects. This is likely due to the low wave heights simulated and therefore lower forces and velocities.
- The inclusion of wave spreading generally reduces the simulated PTO torque. In some sea states, the WEC-Sim results change from over-predicting the measured data to under-predicting it, although the overall effect on the overall percentage difference is relatively small.
- The inclusion of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients generally increases the predicted PTO torque. This is consistent with the findings of the initial MegaRoller loads modelling [D1.2, 2019].
- The inclusion of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients allows the prediction of non-zero mean flap angles, although the predicted mean angles are still significantly lower than the measured data provided, with the simulation generally under-estimating the mean by an average of 67%.
- The updated model, including spread waves and a database of hydrodynamic coefficients, results in a slightly more accurate representation of the measured data, although the difference in overall percentage difference between WEC-Sim and the measured data is small.

More generally, this work suggests that, even for normal operating conditions and relatively benign sea states, WEC-Sim is capable of predicting RMS values of key metrics to within approximately 20%. Differences for extreme events and when considering maximum values are likely to increase, potentially significantly so. For concept design studies, such as MegaRoller, this level of accuracy may be acceptable, especially considering the load factors typically applied which are intended in part to compensate for this uncertainty. However, for detailed design and in-depth optimisation studies, it is likely that further development of these tools would be required (e.g. by calibrating against tank test data or CFD simulations).

In a second exercise, the structural model developed under WP1 was verified by comparing outputs from Code_Aster with a separate finite-element tool. A similar FE model of the MegaRoller flap was built in the FE solver SAP2000, and two static case studies were considered to compare the flap deflections output from both models.

In a FE analysis, finding the correct mesh density is, among other variables, one of the significant parameters to control the accuracy of the results. Typically, a high-density mesh means more accurate results. However, this must be balanced against the available computational resources. In a preliminary step to the verification exercise, the effects of different mesh sizes on the simulation results were investigated. Maximum deflections of the flap were shown to converge as element size was reduced, with similar convergence patterns featured by both FE solvers. A mesh size of 0.5m x 0.5m was chosen as an initial balance between accuracy and computational requirements.

The deformation of the flap estimated by the two FE models was then compared for two static load cases, varying the wave angle. Deformation time-series and deformation maxima at three example points across the width of the flap showed close agreement between the two FE models. Overall, these results provide confidence in the FE model used as part of the WP1.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of the Document

This document constitutes a verification and validation report for the MegaRoller wave energy converter (WEC) numerical model developed under WP1, describing the approach and the results of the comparison of the numerical model with already validated tools and experimental measurements. The numerical models were developed in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) and was documented in [D1.1, 2018] and [D1.2, 2019].

In [D1.1, 2018], a preliminary validation of the model was conducted using data from small-scale models which were tested in a wave tank at Queen's University in Belfast, UK. The present document builds on this preliminary validation exercise using real sea measurement data from the WaveRoller demonstration unit deployed at the Peniche site (Portugal).

In a second exercise, the structural model developed under WP1 was verified by comparing outputs from Code_Aster with a separate finite-element tool.

This deliverable is the main output of Task 1.4, aiming to increase the confidence that the simulation models provide a reliable description of the MegaRoller power take-off (PTO) and the upgraded test bench behaviour in the required conditions.

This document is organised in four (4) main sections. Following this introduction (Section 1), the validation exercise of the numerical loads model developed in Task 1.2 is described in Section 2. Section 3 covers the verification exercises performed for structural model. Finally, key results and recommended next steps are detailed in Section 4.

1.2 Acceptance Criteria

This document adheres to the description of the deliverable provided in the Grant Agreement:

- “Describes the validation activities performed for the loads model. The analysis results of the verification and validation activities shall be presented as well.”

2 LOADS MODEL VALIDATION

Two main exercises were conducted in order to validate the WEC-Sim loads model, as outlined below.

- An initial pre-validation exercise was conducted at the start of the MegaRoller project in 2018, comparing the initial WEC-Sim outputs against measurements from tank tests. This exercise is documented in [D1.1, 2018] and is summarised in Section 2.1.
- An additional validation exercise was conducted in 2020, comparing the updated WEC-Sim model against measurements to real sea measurements obtained from AWE's demonstration unit deployment in 2014. This exercise is summarized in Section 2.2.

It should be noted that the validation exercises were limited by the data available. In particular, data from the test-rig, developed as part of the MegaRoller project, was not available at the time of writing this report.

2.1 Pre-Validation

As part of the initial development of a WEC-Sim loads model, a pre-validation exercise was conducted, comparing the initial WEC-Sim outputs against measurements from tank tests. A summary of the main results and conclusions is included in this section. The full study is documented in [D1.1, 2018].

2.1.1 Background

The case study presented in this section compared the initial WEC-Sim outputs against measurements from tank tests conducted at the Queen's University of Belfast facility between August 2017 and January 2018, using a previous design iteration of the WaveRoller WEC at 1:36 scale. The testing campaign concentrated on recording the loads at multiple locations, mainly on the foundation and the flap, under a wide range of design conditions of varying tides, sea states and wave directions.

The tank tests were conducted within the MaRINET2 project funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, under grant agreement no 731084.

The preliminary validation exercise focused on a comparison of the time-series of PTO torque and flap motion in pitch. Prior to conducting the preliminary validation exercise, the analysis of the tank data identified a number key assumptions and limitations, including:

- The wave gauge measuring the free-surface elevation at the location of the device may not have been deployed at the exact position, as the orientation of the WEC model was updated between calibration and deployment. To mitigate the uncertainty, it is noted that, when comparing the flap motion in pitch, the WEC-Sim time-series outputs were shifted to match the zero-crossing instants with the corresponding times in the experimental measurement signals.
- Overall, it was seen that the free-surface elevation time-series feature a non-zero mean. Moreover, regular wave measurements showed some irregularities in the peaks and troughs, potentially showing tank limitations (e.g. with refraction effects).
- The PTO torque vs. pitch velocity profile measured in the tank showed significant variation with respect to the targeted Coulomb profile, in particular for large waves.
- Scale effects:

- The tank measurements were provided as full-scale equivalent values for comparison with WEC-Sim outputs.
- In K2M's experience, the understanding of the limitations (and of the associated uncertainty) of testing non-performance conditions at small scale is critical when selecting the model scale. In particular, issues such as a distortion of the ratio between inertial and viscous forces may arise at small scales [Cruz, 2008], and the extrapolation of the dominant effects using Froude scaling (that accounts for the ratio between inertial and gravitational forces) should in such cases be considered with caution.

In the following subsections, comparisons between tank measurements and WEC-Sim outputs are presented for a regular wave case (Section 2.1.2) and for an irregular wave case (Section 2.1.3).

2.1.2 Regular Wave Case

This subsection describes the preliminary comparison of the WEC-Sim model outputs with experimental data in regular waves. The target input wave condition was a regular wave with 2m wave height and 10s wave period, in a water depth of 14.5m (all full-scale equivalent).

For validation purposes, the environmental input conditions were defined in the input file as the exact measured time series of free-surface elevation.

Figure 1 illustrates the PTO torque as a function of angular velocity in pitch, as well as the smoothed PTO torque profile input in the PTO block of the WEC-Sim model as a look-up-table.

Figure 1 PTO torque profile: torque value against flap angular velocity in pitch – as measured in the tank (blue) and as input in the WEC-Sim PTO model look-up-table (red) – Test 055A

Figure 2 shows the time series of flap motion and PTO torque extracted from the simulation output and experimental measurements. The under-estimation of the amplitude of motion by WEC-Sim is likely to be related to an under estimation of the drag force – in particular, the current WEC-Sim implementation of the drag force does not take into account the relative velocity between the body and the fluid, but rather the absolute body velocity.

Figure 2 Comparison of time-series of motion in pitch (left) and PTO torque (right) between tank measurement (red) and WEC-Sim estimates (blue) – 150s extract – Test 055A

2.1.3 Irregular Wave Case

This subsection describes the preliminary comparison of the WEC-Sim model outputs with experimental data in irregular waves, with 3.5m wave height and 10s wave period, in a water depth of 14.5m (full-scale equivalent).

The target maximum PTO torque for the case considered is shown in Figure 3 . Figure 3 also displays simultaneous measurements of PTO torque and flap angular velocity in pitch, with the addition of the PTO torque profile input in the PTO block of the WEC-Sim model as a look-up-table. The range of PTO torque observed in the tank reaches instantaneous values substantially larger than the target, with values reaching up to 250% the target value.

Figure 3 PTO torque profile: torque value against flap angular velocity in pitch – as measured in the tank (blue) and as input in the WEC-Sim PTO model look-up-table (red) – Test 049A

Figure 4 shows the time series of flap motion and PTO torque extracted from the simulation output and experimental measurements. Overall, the motion signal output by WEC-Sim matches reasonably well the tank measurements, despite the discrepancies in the PTO torque imposed.

Figure 4 Comparison of time-series of motion in pitch (left) and PTO torque (right) between tank measurement (red) and WEC-Sim estimates (blue) – 150s extract – Test 049A

2.2 Validation

The case studies presented in this section constitute a validation exercise, comparing the numerical outputs from the loads model developed in Task 1.2 and described in [D1.1, 2018] to real sea measurements from the demonstration unit measurement campaign conducted in 2014.

In Section 2.2.1, background information regarding the measurement campaign is provided. Then, the WEC-Sim numerical model used in the validation exercise is described in Section 2.2.3, and the results of the comparisons are presented and discussed in Section 2.2.4.

2.2.1 Measurement Campaign

In 2012 AWE deployed an array of three 100kW WaveRoller demonstration units near Peniche, Portugal, as part of the Surge project funded by the EU under the FP7 programme. As part of the campaign, a deployment configuration with only one panel was tested in 2014. Throughout the deployment campaign, load data on the various parts of the device was collected to validate performance as well as the design load cases through operation in the actual marine environment.

The WaveRoller demonstration unit consisted of a 12m wide prime mover (the ‘flap’) attached to the seabed via a gravity base (the ‘base’). In its single deployment configuration, the device operated in the fully exposed ocean environment, with environmental parameters ranging from:

- Significant wave height H_s : 0.51m – 3.60m.
- Energy period T_e : 6.51s – 13.43s.
- Mean direction $MDIR$: -46.62° – 33.48°.
- Water Depth: 10.61m – 13.76m.

During the deployment campaign, AWE collected the following measured data sets, used for the present validation exercise:

- Flap-mounted strain gauge readings at 5 positions.
- Flap position i.e. pitch angle with respect to vertical.
- PTO torque.

Data was provided as a time-series for each variable, with a time interval between measurements of 20ms. The data was provided for 85 different sea states recorded for a length of 20 minutes. Figure 2.5 illustrates the variation in H_s , T_e and water depth covered by the provided sea states.

Figure 2.5 Sea states available for the validation exercise: scatter diagram of significant wave height with energy period for all water depths (left), and of significant wave height with water depth for all energy periods (right).

As shown in Figure 2.5, the available sea states can be categorised into three main groups of water depth. A separate NEMOH simulation was run for each group in order to capture the differences in the flap's hydrodynamic response at different water levels. The mean depth from each group was used as follows:

- Group A – mean depth = 10.7m
- Group B – mean depth = 12.2m
- Group C – mean depth = 13.7m

2.2.2 Limitations on the Measured Data

Prior to conducting the preliminary validation exercise, the analysis of the data available identified a number of key limitations regarding the measured data provided, including:

- Water depth:
 - It is assumed that the water depths provided are still water depths (i.e. excluding the effect of waves).
- Wave data:
 - Information on the wave conditions was provided as spectral data. The significant wave height, energy period and mean direction of propagation was derived for each set of 20 minutes interval.
 - No time-history of the local surface elevation at or close to the device was provided. This prevented any direct comparisons of the time-series and instead limited the validation exercise to comparing average and RMS values, which are generally less dependent on the exact time-series.
 - K2M understands that the mean direction of propagation derived from the ADCP deployed at the site showed an offset error of about 65° , consistent with time. When using the ADCP data to derive a spreading function (see Section 2.2.3.5), a correction

was applied to the data so that the mean direction of the data aligned exactly with the provided sea state mean direction, *MDIR*.

- PTO torque:
 - The measured PTO torque vs. pitch velocity profile showed significant variation with respect to the targeted linear profile (see also Section 2.2.3.4).
 - The PTO torque constant used in the model is derived from the PTO torque vs. flap velocity. Measurement errors may therefore lead to errors on the PTO torque value.
- Overall, limited information on the accuracy of the measured data was provided.

2.2.3 Baseline WEC-Sim Model

2.2.3.1 Overview

The load validation effort was conducted using a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim, introduced in Task 1.2 [D1.1, 2018]. WEC-Sim is a multi-body numerical simulation tool designed for the analysis of WECs. Typical use can be for the estimation of hydrodynamic loads and assessment of PTO performance. The program is integrated in MATLAB within the Simulink module, which allows operations to be driven in a graphical programming environment. It provides the ability to model devices that are comprised of rigid bodies, joints, PTOs and mooring systems by using pre-defined block diagrams.

A linear model of the WaveRoller demonstration unit WEC was developed in WEC-Sim. Essentially, the WEC can be described as an oscillating wave surge converter (OWSC) with a hydraulic PTO, operating in nearshore regions at depths of between 8 and 20 meters, approximately 0.3-2km from the shore. The device is anchored to the seabed and, depending on tidal conditions, it is mostly or fully submerged during operation. The following subsections describe the structural, hydrodynamic, PTO and wave models, as well as the numerical input for the simulations considered.

2.2.3.2 Structural Model

The model presents a few changes compared to the model developed in e.g. [D1.1, 2018]. In particular, dimensions, masses, hydrodynamic properties and PTO forces were updated.

The Simulink model of the WaveRoller device is presented in Figure 2.6. The structural model differs from the previous model [D1.1, 2018] in that the connectivity between the prime mover ('flap') and the gravity base ('base') bodies is made via a rotational hinge joint, in which PTO properties are assigned. The connectivity to the seabed remains via a fixed constraint.

Figure 2.6: Simulink model of the WaveRoller demonstration unit device.

Location coordinates of the various blocks are defined with respect to the global reference frame, as shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Body CoG locations in Z (heave) direction, relative to the seabed.

Body	Heave CoG (m, relative to the Seabed)
Fixed constraint - constraint(1)	0
Base - Body (2)	+1.863
Rotational joint - pto(1)	+3.367
Flap - body(1)	+7.131

A geometry file of the flap was provided by AWE in a STEP (.stp) format, which subsequently was subjected to minor alterations in order to simplify the geometry and reduce computational effort. These alterations involved the removal of features which are considered negligible for the hydrodynamic and load estimation simulations, such as fillets, chamfers and holes. These original flap geometry as well as the simplified version are presented respectively in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Original (left) and simplified (right) flap.

The mass and inertia properties of the flap, which were extracted from the provided CAD model, are listed Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Geometry, buoyancy and inertia properties of the flap.

Mass (kg)	Displaced Volume (m ³)	CB (rel. to seabed)	Moments of inertia (kg m ² , about CG)
21853	18.26	(0, 0, 7.131)	(4.46E+06, 1.88E+05, 2.74E+05)

2.2.3.3 Hydrodynamic Model

The hydrodynamic coefficients for the flap were derived using NEMOH and subsequently imported in the WEC-Sim model, in a similar approach to that described in [D1.1, 2018].

As NEMOH cannot accurately model thin panels, the flap thickness was increased to allow more accurate modelling. Corresponding adjustments to the mass (i.e. by adjusting the material density) were made to give the same net buoyancy as the original design. The mesh used for the water depth group B (12.2m) is presented in Figure 2.8. The mesh was shifted vertically for the other water depth groups, and NEMOH simulations were run to obtain the hydrodynamic coefficients in all cases.

Figure 2.8: Mesh of the flap generated for NEMOH.

Viscous drag forces were included in the model through the use of drag coefficients and representative areas. As a first approximation, and following the approach described in [D1.2, 2019], the drag force acting on the WaveRoller WEC prime mover can be included in the equation of motion and estimated using a Morison based quadratic term:.

$$F_{visc} = 0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot v^2 \cdot C_d$$

Where v , A and C_d are the velocity, characteristic area and drag coefficient vectors, respectively, with separate values specified for each co-ordinate direction. The following coefficients were initially approximated as follows, where w , h and t are the width (12.1m), height (8.5m) and thickness (approximated as 1m) of the flap respectively:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} wh & 0 & wt & 0 & \frac{wh^4}{4} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_d = [1.2 \ 0 \ 1.2 \ 0 \ 1.2 \ 0]$$

In Section 2.2.4.5 , alternative characteristic area and drag coefficient vectors are also considered in order to evaluate the sensitivity of the model to the drag formulation. In particular, the implementation proposed by DNV-GL in [DNV, 215] was considered, varying the drag coefficient between 1.2 (value requested by AWE in [D1.2, 2019]) and 2.0 (value applicable for a long plate in high Reynolds numbers).

2.2.3.4 Power Take-Off Model

Linear Model

The PTO was initially modelled as a linear damper, where the PTO torque varies linearly with the rotational speed of the flap:

$$M_{PTO} = c_{PTO} \cdot -\omega_{flap}$$

AWE only provided an estimation of the PTO torque constant, c_{PTO} , within a range of 1MN/rad. For the simulation in each sea state, the value actually achieved was therefore estimated separately using the time-series of flap position and PTO torque provided by AWE. Rotational velocity was first derived by differentiating the position time-series. The torque constant was then derived by fitting a linear (straight-line) graph to the plot of flap velocity v PTO torque, as illustrated in Figure 2.9.

In general, the derived torque constant was within the range specified by AWE, providing confidence in the results. Overall, the PTO torque response was close to linear, with the data being distributed closely near its linear fit, with an R-squared value greater than 0.9 for all sea states and an average R-squared value of 0.939. However, in a number of cases the response was significantly away from the expected linear profile, as can be seen in Figure 2.9 where several outliers can be observed. Therefore, the linear model implemented is only an approximation of the actual PTO response, and such approximation may be one potential cause for discrepancies between the measured data and the WEC-Sim simulations – see also Section 2.2.4. It should also be noted that relatively small errors in the flap position measurement may have a large effect on the derived values for velocity and therefore torque constant.

Figure 2.9 Distribution of the PTO torque with the flap rotational velocity for sea state 0716 : the slope of the fitted curve provides the PTO damping constant to input in the PTO model.

Force Cap Implementation

As a second step in the validation study the PTO module was updated to include a force cap. To implement the force cap in the WEC-Sim model, the PTO module was updated to use the *If statement* as follows:

If $abs(c_{PTO} \cdot \omega_{flap}) > 1MNm$:

$$M_{PTO} = -sign(\omega_{flap}) \cdot 1 MNm$$

Else:

$$M_{PTO} = c_{PTO} \cdot -\omega_{flap}$$

It should be noted that the cap is still relatively simplistic and assumes the controller can achieve the desired profile exactly, with no over- or under-shoot.

2.2.3.5 WEC-Sim Simulation Setup and Wave Model

Key input parameters for the WEC-Sim simulations are shown in Table 2.3. Simulations were performed for the three water groups (10.7m, 12.2m and 13.7m, see Section 2.2.3.3). The length of the simulated time series was set to 1300s and a time step of 0.01s was used. A ramp-up period of 100s was used for all simulations. It should be noted that the data used for post-processing excluded the ramp-up period (i.e. 1200s, the same length as each measured data time-series record).

Table 2.3 WEC-Sim simulation parameters.

Simulation length (s)	1300
Ramp-up time (s)	100
Time step (s)	0.01
Hydrodynamic solver	Linear

For each sea state considered, the linear damping coefficient used by the demonstration unit was applied in the numerical simulation (see Section 2.2.3.4).

For each sea state considered, the measured wave spectrum provided by AWE was used as an input to WEC-Sim to derive a free-surface elevation time series. The provided spectra contained 49 frequencies, equally spaced in the interval 0.02-0.49Hz. The number of frequencies was increased to 400 using linear interpolation and extrapolation such that WEC-Sim had a sufficient number of frequencies to generate an irregular sea state. In a preliminary step, the unidirectional amplitude spectrum was used as input. In a second step, the directional spectrum was used (see Section 2.2.4.6).

In previous versions of the WEC-Sim code, the waves were assumed to be unidirectional. In [D1.2, 2019], a customised extension for WEC-Sim was developed to model wave spreading. More recently, NREL has released an update to the WEC-Sim code (V4.0) that includes an in-built wave spreading function. The NREL formulation requires the user to specify a series of wave directions and a percentage occurrence for each direction (summing to 100%). The directional spectra provided by AWE contain the percentage of occurrence of each direction (0-360° in 4° segments) for each frequency in the spectrum. To approximate a spreading function for each sea state, the occurrence data provided by AWE was binned into the following directions, where θ_0 is the mean direction.

$$\theta = \theta_0 - 36 : 4 : \theta_0 + 36$$

Limiting the function to $\pm 36^\circ$ of spread was necessary so that a range of sea states could be considered, as NEMOH data was only produced for $\pm 45^\circ$ and several sea states had a mean direction of up to $\pm 15^\circ$.

2.2.3.6 Limitations on the WEC-Sim Model

When analysing the results of the preliminary validation exercise, the following key limitations regarding the WEC-Sim model should be considered:

- WEC-Sim models deep-water, linear (airy) waves. The demonstration unit was deployed in relatively shallow water. The effect of wave shoaling and any non-linearity in the wave was not considered in WEC-Sim.
- In the current formulation, a number of physical processes are not accounted for in WEC-Sim, including:
 - Mean drift forces.
 - Current loads.
 - Friction.
 - Deformation of key linkages.
 - Other external factors (e.g. marine growth).
- NEMOH cannot model thin panels and the flap thickness was therefore artificially increased (see Section 2.2.3.3).
 - The increased thickness of the flap may lead to inaccuracies in the hydrodynamic coefficients.
 - In future work, a more advanced hydrodynamic solver (e.g. WAMIT) could be used.
- The geometry of the gravity base was not modelled explicitly and therefore body-to-body interactions between the base and prime mover could not be included.

2.2.4 Hydrodynamic Validation

This section presents the results of the preliminary hydrodynamic modelling validation exercise conducted using the baseline WEC-Sim model described in Section 2.2.3. The WEC-Sim outputs are first compared to the measured data provided by AWE (Section 2.2.4.1). A series of sensitivity studies were then conducted, investigating the impact of the following parameters on the results:

- The wave input seeds (Section 2.2.4.2).
- Non-linear modelling (Section 2.2.4.3)
- The complexity of the PTO model, in particular with the inclusion of a force cap (Section 2.2.4.4).
- The drag formulation (Section 2.2.4.5).
- The consideration of wave spreading (Section 2.2.4.6)
- The implementation of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients (Section 2.2.4.7).

Based on the results of these studies, the WEC-Sim model was then refined, and an updated validation study was performed, as presented in Section 2.2.4.8 .

2.2.4.1 Preliminary Investigations

Initial simulations were run using the baseline WEC-Sim model defined in Section 2.2.3. Three key metrics were considered:

- Mean position of the flap [deg].
- RMS of the flap position [deg].
- RMS of the PTO torque [Nm].

Figure 2.10 shows the mean pitch angle of the flap from the measured data (in blue) and WEC-Sim output (in red). A clear difference can be seen, with the measured data showing a consistent non-zero mean position of up to 35°, whereas the WEC-Sim simulations oscillate about a pitch angle close to the starting position of 0°. The non-zero mean pitch angle observed in the measurements may be due to drift forces or current loads that are not currently accounted for in the WEC-Sim model.

Figure 2.10 Distribution of the mean flap pitch angle with the significant wave height: measured (blue) and simulated values (red).

Figure 2.11 shows the RMS of the measured PTO torque against the simulated value for each sea state. Figure 2.14 shows a similar plot for the RMS of the flap pitch angle. The dashed line represents perfect correlation between the two models. With the exception of three clear outliers (circled), the two data sets are generally well matched.

Figure 2.11 Distribution of the simulated RMS PTO torque with the measured RMS PTO torque.

Figure 2.12 Distribution of the simulated RMS pitch angle with the measured RMS pitch angle (outliers not plotted).

The three outliers all relate to the 10.7m water depth case, with the following sea states:

- Sea State 1316 – $H_s = 1.66$, $T_e = 10.93$
- Sea State 1318 – $H_s = 1.72$, $T_e = 10.64$
- Sea State 1319 – $H_s = 1.96$, $T_e = 10.65$

From Figure 2.5, these three sea states are also outliers in terms of their H_s , which is much larger than all other sea states at this depth. It is possible that there are numerical errors in these sets of measured data. These values were excluded from the analysis below and in the following sensitivity studies.

Figure 2.13 and Figure 2.14 show the percentage difference between the measured and simulated results for each metric, with data points coloured by the three water depth groups used. Table 2.4 shows the average (absolute) percentage differences.

Overall, the WEC-Sim model produces reasonable results, with an average difference of approximately 15%. However, large differences of up to 40% can be observed in some sea states. In general, WEC-Sim tends to over-predict both metrics from the measured data in the 10.7m and 12.2m water depth groups, whilst the results appear overall underpredicted in the 13.7m case. The largest variations (in absolute values) are for the 10.7m group, suggesting that interaction with and proximity of the flap to the free surface is a potential reason for the discrepancies seen (e.g. the flap piercing the free surface, wave breaking).

Looking at the 12.2m case, that presents the largest variability in significant wave height, the range of percentage difference between the measured and simulated results appear similar for small and large significant wave heights suggesting that non-linear effects due to larger waves did not have a significant impact on the results.

Figure 2.13 Distribution of the percentage difference between measured and simulated RMS PTO torque, per groups of water depth: 10.7m (red), 12.2m (blue) and 13.7m (green).

Figure 2.14 Distribution of the percentage difference between measured and simulated RMS flap position (pitch angle), per groups of water depth: 10.7m (red), 12.2m (blue) and 13.7m (green).

Table 2.4 Absolute percentage difference between measured and simulated values of RMS PTO torque and RMS flap position (pitch angle).

Water Depth Group (m)	RMS PTO Torque	RMS Flap Position
10.7	18.2%	19.6%
12.2	9.7%	13.2%
13.7	14.0%	12.7%
All sea states	13.2%	14.9%

In the following sub-sections, the influence of a range of key parameters on the metrics of interest are investigated, in an effort to improve the accuracy of the model.

2.2.4.2 Sensitivity Study 1: Use of Different Wave Seeds

As discussed in Section 2.2.1, the wave elevation time series were not available for this validation exercise. The results may therefore be sensitive to the input seed used to create the time series for each sea state. The first sensitivity study conducted aimed to assess the sensitivity of the PTO torque to the input wave seed. Two additional input seeds were run to give a total of three independent simulations per sea state.

The PTO torque results estimated using each seed is shown in Figure 2.15 for 40 example sea states. Some larger differences (up to approximately 9%, e.g. for sea state 699) between seeds can be observed, but overall all seeds lead to similar torque estimates. Table 2.5 shows the percentage difference in the RMS PTO torque observed for each seed. Differences between seeds are in average less than 3 percentage points, suggesting that the input seed does not have a significant impact on the overall results. This suggests that a single input seed may be sufficient for preliminary, high-level analysis. In the next sensitivity studies (Sections 2.2.4.3 to 2.2.4.7), a single, fixed seed was used for each sea state to allow direct comparisons between each set of results.

Figure 2.15 PTO torque values for each sea considered (seed 1 in blue, seed 2 in red, seed 3 in green) for 40 example sea states.

Table 2.5 Absolute average percentage difference in RMS PTO torque for each input seed, for each water depth group.

Water Depth Group (m)	Seed 1	Seed 2	Seed 3
10.7	18.2%	19.7%	20.4%
12.2	9.7%	10.9%	11.7%
13.7	14.0%	14.3%	13.8%
All sea states	13.2%	14.3%	14.8%

2.2.4.3 Sensitivity Study 2: Non-Linear Modelling

As described in Section 2.2.3.3, the baseline WEC-Sim model is fundamentally linear. However, WEC-Sim also has the capability to include weakly non-linear hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov forces, whereby the calculated based on the device position at each time-step. A sensitivity study was conducted to assess the impact of this for the 10.7m water group. In principle this group is most likely to be affected by such non-linearities as the top of the flap is closest to the free-surface.

Table 2.6 shows the percentage difference in PTO torque. Due to the computational time required for non-linear simulations, this sensitivity was run using shorter (5 minute) simulations and so the results are not comparable with the other sections of this report. In general, including non-linear effects is shown to have only a small benefit. This is likely due to the relatively small wave heights considered in this study, which mean that the flap rarely pierces the free-surface.

Table 2.6 Absolute percentage difference in RMS PTO torque for the baseline case (linear) and the case with non-linear effects

Water Depth (m)	Baseline	Non-Linear
10.7	29.9%	29.4%

2.2.4.4 Sensitivity Study 3: Inclusion of a Force Cap

As described in Section 2.2.3.4, the initial simulations used a simplified, linear representation of the PTO response. In a second step, a force cap was implemented in the PTO model for a more realistic representation of the target profile, where the PTO torque does not exceed 1MNm. A sensitivity study was conducted to investigate the effect of this force cap on the results.

Table 2.7 shows the percentage difference in PTO torque. When compared with the linear case, it is clear that the force cap has had very little effect on the torque. This is likely due to the relatively small wave heights considered in this study, with forces being rarely large enough to activate the cap (see also Figure 2.16), therefore limiting the effect on the RMS values.

Table 2.7 Absolute percentage difference in RMS PTO torque for the baseline case (linear PTO) and the case without a force cap

Water Depth (m)	Baseline	With Force Cap
10.7	18.2%	18.2%
12.2	9.7%	9.7%
13.7	14.0%	14.0%
All sea states	13.2%	13.2%

Figure 2.16 shows the measured PTO torque from all sea states. Occurrences of the PTO ‘over-shooting’ the 1MNm target torque cap can be observed, although it should be noted that the majority of the sea states recorded do not reach the cap, as highlighted by the circled region. In future work, a more sophisticated PTO model could be implemented to capture such exceedance of cap.

Figure 2.16 Distribution of the measured PTO torque with the measured flap rotational velocity for all recorded sea states.

2.2.4.5 Sensitivity Study 4 Drag Formulation

The baseline model used a viscous drag formulation based on K2M’s previous modelling of other OWSC’s (see Section 2.2.3.3). However, previous validation work completed by DNV-GL [DNV, 2015], used an alternative formulation as shown below, where coefficients were only specified in the pitch direction:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{wh^4}{4} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_d = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1.2 \ 0]$$

The simulations we re-run to investigate the sensitivity of the results to this parameter, varying the drag coefficient between 1.2 (value requested by AWE in [D1.2, 2019]) and 2.0 (value applicable for a long plate in high Reynolds numbers).

As shown in Table 2.8, changing the formulation generally had a small effect on the overall PTO torque results. The results appear to be relatively insensitive to the viscous drag forces. This is likely due to the relatively low wave heights considered, which leads to low flap rotational velocities and viscous forces regardless of the formulation used.

Table 2.8 Absolute percentage difference in PTO torque for the baseline model and the updated drag formulation.

Water Depth Group (m)	Baseline	Updated drag formulation (DNV-GL)	
		$C_d = 1.2$	$C_d = 2.0$
10.7	18.2%	18.5%	17.8%
12.2	9.7%	10.0%	9.7%
13.7	14.0%	13.7%	14.4%
All sea states	13.2%	13.4%	13.2%

2.2.4.6 Sensitivity Study 5: Use of Spread Waves

In the baseline WEC-Sim formulation, the waves are assumed to be unidirectional. In reality, it is likely that the incoming waves present some level of directional spreading, with waves approaching from a range of angles during the same sea state. This sensitivity study aims to assess the influence of the directional spreading on the RMS PTO torque.

Wave spread was modelled using the updated WEC-Sim formulation (v4.0) as described in Section 2.2.3.5 . Only a reduced set of 20 sea states, all from the 12.2 water depth group, were considered for this study due to limitations with the NEMOH data, which only included incoming wave angles up to +/-45°. The baseline values reported in this section are therefore different from previous sections, as they consider only the 20 sea states analysed.

Figure 2.17 and Table 2.9 show the effect of including wave spreading on the RMS PTO torque. Wave spreading generally reduces the RMS torque. Where RMS torque was over-estimated by the baseline model, the percentage difference between the measured and simulated data reduces, and vice-versa for cases where the baseline model under-estimated the RMS torque. The overall change in percentage difference is therefore small.

Figure 2.17 Distribution of the percentage difference in RMS PTO torque: results from the baseline model (blue) and from the model considering spread waves (red), for a reduced set of simulations

Table 2.9 Absolute percentage difference in PTO torque for the baseline model and the model with spread waves for a reduced set of simulations

Water Depth Group (m)	Baseline	With Spread Waves
Reduced num. of sea states (12.2m)	8.3%	7.9%

2.2.4.7 Sensitivity Study 6: Use of a Hydrodynamic Database

During the initial loads modelling of the MegaRoller device [D1.2, 2019], an extension of the WEC-Sim source code was developed to enable the use of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients. To account for the change in hydrodynamic properties with the pitching motion of the flap, the model can calculate the hydrodynamic forces using the hydrodynamic coefficients derived at the closest angle available in the database. The database approach is further documented in [D1.2, 2019].

In this study, coefficients were generated using NEMOH in 10° increments from -30° to 30°.

Figure 2.18 and Table 2.10 show the effect of including the database on the percentage difference in RMS PTO torque. Use of the database increases the RMS torque for all sea states, suggesting that the nominal

(0°) hydrodynamic coefficients under-predict the response at larger pitch angles. This matches the findings of the MegaRoller loads analysis [D1.2, 2019].

The baseline model tended to over-predict the RMS torque for most of the sea states considered in this sensitivity study. The use of the database further exacerbates this, leading to larger percentage differences. However, when combined with other model adjustments (e.g. wave spread) the effect may be more beneficial (see also Section 2.2.4.8).

Figure 2.18 Distribution of the percentage difference in RMS PTO torque: results from the baseline model (red) and from the model with the database (blue).

Table 2.10 Absolute percentage difference in RMS PTO torque for the baseline model and the model with the database.

Water Depth Group (m)	Baseline	With Database
Reduced num. of sea states (12.2m)	8.3%	12.6%

2.2.4.8 Updated Model Validation

As a final step, the various model enhancements tested in the previous sections were added to the baseline model and tested in combination. Changes which were shown to have only a minimal impact were not included. Overall, the following settings were used:

- Single fixed wave seed
- Addition of a force cap to the PTO controller.
- Baseline drag formulation.
- Consideration of spread waves.
- Inclusion of a hydrodynamic database

Figure 2.19 illustrates the impact of the WEC-Sim model changes on the PTO torque. The updated model tends to predict a lower RMS torque than the baseline model (see Table 2.10). When compared with the measured data, the overall difference in RMS torque is very similar.

The trends are different when considering the RMS of the flap angular position (see Figure 2.20). The updated model is seen to result in larger RMS values and larger differences when compared to the measured data (see Table 2.11). However, it should be noted that the use of the updated model leads to non-zero mean flap positions (see Figure 2.21). The predicted means are still lower than the measured values, but the use of the database at least allows non-zero means to be simulated, whereas all previous model iterations resulted in a mean position close to 0° for all sea states.

Overall, these results suggest that the enhancements made to the WEC-Sim model during the MegaRoller project are slightly beneficial in terms of increasing the accuracy of the predicted PTO torque and position, although there are still differences of up to 25% between the measured and simulated data when considering individual sea states.

It should also be noted this final set of simulations with the updated model were only run for the 12.2m water depth. The effects at other water depths are unknown. It could be expected that the general tendency of the updated model to reduce RMS torque could lead to reduced differences for the 10.7m water depth, where the baseline model tended to over-estimate the measured data. However, the opposite effect may be seen for the 13.7m water depth, where the baseline model tended to under-estimate the measured data.

Figure 2.19 Distribution of the percentage difference in RMS PTO torque with the significant wave height for all sea states: results from the baseline model (green), updated model without the database (purple) and updated model with the database (red).

Figure 2.20 Distribution of the percentage difference in RMS flap pitch angle with the significant wave height for all sea states: results from the baseline model (green), updated model without the database (purple) and updated model with the database (red).

Figure 2.21 Distribution of the mean flap mean pitch angle [deg] with the significant wave height for all sea states: results from the measurements at sea (green), the baseline model (purple), updated model without the database (red) and updated model with the database (blue).

Table 2.11 Average absolute percentage differences in RMS PTO torque and RMS flap position for the baseline model, the updated model without the database and the updated model with the database.

Absolute Percentage Difference	Baseline	Updated
RMS PTO Torque	8.3%	8.2%
RMS Flap Position	10.4%	22.9%

2.3 Conclusions and Recommendations

The following high-level conclusions can be drawn from the preliminary hydrodynamic validation exercise and sensitivity studies presented in this section:

- The PTO torque is relatively insensitive to the viscous drag formulation, PTO force cap and consideration of non-linear effects. This is likely due to the low wave heights simulated and therefore lower forces and velocities.
- The inclusion of wave spreading generally reduces the simulated PTO torque. In some sea states, the WEC-Sim results change from over-predicting the measured data to under-predicting it, although the overall effect on the overall percentage difference is relatively small.
- The inclusion of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients generally increases the predicted PTO torque. This is consistent with the findings of the initial MegaRoller loads modelling [D1.2, 2019].
- The inclusion of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients allows the prediction of non-zero mean flap angles, although the predicted mean angles are still significantly lower than the measured data provided, with the simulation generally under-estimating the mean by an average of 67%.
- The updated model, including spread waves and a database of hydrodynamic coefficients, results in a slightly more accurate representation of the measured data, although the difference in overall percentage difference between WEC-Sim and the measured data is small.

More generally, this work suggests that, for normal operating conditions and relatively benign sea states, WEC-Sim is capable of predicting RMS values of key metrics to within approximately 20%. Differences for extreme events and when considering maximum values are likely to increase, potentially significantly so. For concept design studies, such as MegaRoller, this level of accuracy may be acceptable, especially considering the load factors typically applied, which are intended in part to compensate for this uncertainty. However, for detailed design and in-depth optimisation studies, it is likely that further development of these tools would be required (e.g. by calibrating against tank test data or CFD simulations).

3 STRUCTURAL MODEL VERIFICATION

By default, WEC-Sim follows a rigid-body approach to estimate the dynamic response of a WEC system, where each body is treated as a point mass with mass and inertia properties. To allow deformation of the MegaRoller prime-mover, or flap, which in turn may influence the loads calculation, a structural dynamics module was developed and implemented. The module incorporates a Finite Element (FE) representation of the MegaRoller flap and enables coupled hydro-elastic assessments. The module, based on the FE solver Code_Aster, is documented in deliverable 1.2 [D1.2, 2019] as well as in a conference paper submitted to the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC) [Scriven, 2019].

This section documents a preliminary verification of the structural model developed, comparing the results from Code_Aster with results from a separate FE program, SAP2000. The model inputs and assumptions are documented in Section 3.1. Results are then presented in Section 3.2, followed by a list of key conclusions and recommendations in Section 3.3.

3.1 Model Build

3.1.1 Assumed Geometry

MegaRoller is still in the early stages of development and therefore limited information regarding the structural design is available. The overall outline design for the structural model is shown in Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2. The flap's shape and dimensions (2.5m x 30m x 10m) were provided by AWE¹. The bearings, connecting the flap to the foundation, were represented using two blocks (2.5m x 3m x 2m) at each side of the flap. The connection between the bearings and the flap is indicated as "PTO interfaces" in Figure 3.1.

It was then assumed that the internal structure comprises of 2 horizontal and 9 vertical stiffeners – see Figure 3.2. All panels were assumed to be 25mm thick and manufactured from S355 steel (Young's modulus $E = 210GPa$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$).

Figure 3.1 External view of the MegaRoller flap geometry

¹ M. Vuorinen (2018), [1072] MEGAROLLER WP1 - WEC-Sim model: pre-validation and verification input, [E-mail] message to P. Laporte-Weywada, dated 23/05/2018

Figure 3.2 Internal view of the assumed MegaRoller flap geometry

3.1.2 Loads Model & Load Cases

The WEC-Sim model of the MegaRoller OWSC, developed to enable loads calculations, was used for this study. At a high level, the numerical model consists of a hydrodynamic body representing the gravity base, connected to the seabed via a fixed constraint, and to the prime mover (the flap) via a pitching constraint (mimicking the bearings). Two PTO subsystems, located between the bearings and the flap, include a translational PTO block. The model is further described in [D1.2, 2019].

In the present verification exercise, two load cases were considered. Both cases focused on an uncoupled, static analysis of the MegaRoller OWSC, and all DoFs were restrained at the bearings and PTO interfaces to simulate the flap being locked in position. The load cases considered an irregular sea state, defined as a JONSWAP spectrum with significant wave height H_s of 2.75m and a peak period T_p of 11.5s, and the load cases are only differentiated by the incident wave angle:

- In Load Case 1, the waves are approaching in a direction normal to the flap.
- In Load Case 2, the waves are approaching in a 45° angled direction from the normal to the flap.

The key parameters considered in the WEC-Sim simulation are summarised in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 WEC-Sim simulation parameters

Spectrum shape	JONSWAP, $\gamma=3.3$
H_s [m]	2.75
T_p [s]	11.5
Simulation length [s]	500
Time step [s]	0.01

3.1.3 Surface Pressure Derivation

Structural analysis tools such as SAP2000 or Code_Aster require the input of all the relevant distributed pressure loads to enable the capture of any difference in loading across the flap. By default, WEC-Sim outputs forces and moments at a single reference point on each body (usually the centre of gravity). When using the ‘non-linear’ formulation, this is extended to include distributed hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov pressures, mapped on to a *.stl* panel mesh which must be provided.

The baseline WEC-Sim formulation was extended as part of the MegaRoller project to include estimations for the surface pressure due to other force components. This was based on previous work by [Michelen, 2016].

The methodology followed for each force component is detailed below.

Diffraction

Diffraction pressures were generated using the diffraction pressure coefficients calculated by NEMOH. The method provided in [Michelen, 2016] was extended to allow for irregular sea states using the following equation:

$$P_{df_i} = \sum_{j=1}^n A_{\omega} [\operatorname{Re}\{C_{df_i}(\omega_j, \theta_j)\} * \cos(\omega_j t + \varphi_j) + \operatorname{Im}\{C_{df_i}(\omega_j, \theta_j)\} * \sin(\omega_j t + \varphi_j)]$$

Added Mass

In a similar manner, added mass pressures were calculated using the imaginary part of the radiation pressure coefficients output from NEMOH. In this case, the coefficients at the highest frequency analysed (4Hz) were used as an approximation of the added mass at infinite frequency in conjunction with the equation below:

$$P_{am_i} = \sum_{j=1}^{j=6} \ddot{x}_j \cdot \frac{-\operatorname{Im}\{C_{rad_i}\}_{4\text{Hz}}}{\omega}$$

Radiation

The method presented in [Michelen, 2016] for calculating radiation pressures is only applicable for regular sea states where the Convolution Integral (CI) formulation ('fluid memory effect') is not included. For more general, irregular sea states the radiation pressures on each cell cannot easily be generated using the NEMOH coefficients. The equations below were therefore used as an initial approximation, scaling the coefficients for a single frequency (0.1Hz was used in this example) to match the point force output by WEC-Sim.

$$P_{rad, 0.1\text{Hz}_i} = \sum_{j=1}^{j=6} \dot{x}_j \cdot \operatorname{Re}\{C_{rad_i}\}_{0.1\text{Hz}}$$

$$F_{x_{int}} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=\text{num cells}} P_{rad, 0.1\text{Hz}_i} \cdot \widehat{n}_{x_i} \cdot A_i$$

$$P_{rad_i} = P_{rad, 0.1\text{Hz}_i} \cdot \frac{F_{x_{rad}}}{F_{x_{int}}}$$

Viscous Drag

Viscous drag forces in WEC-sim are calculated using a single drag coefficient. Deriving a distribution of pressures due to viscous drag is therefore not possible without conducting a higher fidelity assessment (e.g. CFD). For this study, the viscous drag force was applied using the same distribution derived for added mass. The pressure on each panel was scaled such that the total surge (F_x) force matched the point load output from WEC-Sim.

$$P_{visc_i} = P_{am_i} \cdot \frac{F_{x_{visc}}}{F_{x_{am}}}$$

Finally, the total pressure on each panel was taken as the sum of each component:

$$P_{tot_i} = P_{exc_i} + P_{hs_i} + P_{am_i} + P_{rad_i} + P_{visc_i}$$

3.1.4 Time-step Selection

In a static structural assessment, the results at each individual time step do not depend on the results at the previous time steps. As such, the assessment does not require the analysis of every WEC-Sim simulation time steps, as long as a sufficient number of events are considered to adequately capture the structural response.

An iterative process was applied to select a set of relevant structural time steps: the process aimed to minimise the sample size (i.e. number of points selected) while limiting to 250kN (~2.5% of the peak force) the maximum difference in total force in surge between the WEC-Sim solution and the coarser time-series obtained by linearly interpolating between the selected points. Figure 3.3 shows the final selection of 458 points for Load Case 1, compared to a total of 50,000 time steps in the WEC-Sim time signal. This process was repeated for Load Case 2.

Figure 3.3 Selection of points (red dots) from the WEC-Sim results (black line)

These were applied as nodal forces at discrete points on the external surface of the flap, in the axial (X) direction only for Load Case 1, or in both axial (X) and transversal (Y) direction for Load Case 2 (as a result of the angled wave loading input).

3.1.5 SAP2000 Model

This section presents the FE model setup built in SAP2000 Ultimate Version 21.0.2 FEA software. SAP2000 (Structural Analysis Program) software, a structural analysis program developed by Computer and Structures, Inc² (CSI), allows three-dimensional static and dynamic analysis, linear or nonlinear, of a wide range of structures using a FE modelling method. In this section, the SAP2000 FE model characteristics and boundary conditions are described.

3.1.5.1 Model Characteristics

The MegaRoller FE model was built in SAP2000 using shell elements to represent the structural components of the flap. All shell elements were defined as thin panels with a thickness of 25mm and

² <https://www.csiamerica.com/products/sap2000>

assigned a linear-elastic steel material property (steel grade S355 material, with Young's modulus $E = 210\text{GPa}$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$).

To investigate the effects of mesh density on the results, four different resolutions were considered to create the mesh of the flap: a coarse resolution of $3.0\text{m} \times 1.7\text{m}$, a medium resolution of $1.5\text{m} \times 1.67\text{m}$ (see Figure 3.4 a), a finer resolution of $0.5\text{m} \times 0.5\text{m}$ (see Figure 3.4 b) and a dense resolution of $0.25\text{m} \times 0.25\text{m}$. The key results and findings of the mesh density assessment are described in Section 3.2.1. For the verification exercise, and following the initial mesh density study, the finer mesh ($0.5\text{m} \times 0.5\text{m}$ element size) was used.

Figure 3.4 MegaRoller model in SAP2000: a) mesh size $1.67\text{m} \times 1.5\text{m}$, b) mesh size $0.5\text{m} \times 0.5\text{m}$

3.1.6 Code_Aster Model

This section presents the FE model setup built in Code_Aster Version 13.6 FEA software. Code_Aster, an open-source Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software package developed by EDF-Energy, supports both static and dynamic analysis, linear or nonlinear, for a wide range of structures. The open-source code allows modification if required and Python scripting can be used to automate pre- and post-processing. In addition, the solver can be used in conjunction with Salome-Meca³, an open-source geometry and meshing tool. In this section, the Code_Aster FE model characteristics and boundary conditions are described.

3.1.6.1 Model Characteristics

The MegaRoller geometry was built in Code_Aster using DKT shell elements. DKT shell elements are 4-noded, linear shell elements suitable for modelling flat surfaces where the through-thickness dimension is much smaller than the other two dimensions (i.e., a thin plate).

Similar to the SAP2000 model, four different resolutions were considered to create the mesh of the flap in order to investigate the effect of mesh density: a coarse mesh ($3.0\text{m} \times 1.7\text{m}$ element size), a medium mesh ($1.5\text{m} \times 1.7\text{m}$ element size), a finer mesh ($0.5\text{m} \times 0.5\text{m}$ element size, see Figure 3.5) and a dense resolution of $0.25\text{m} \times 0.25\text{m}$. Following the initial mesh density study, the finer mesh ($0.5\text{m} \times 0.5\text{m}$ element size) was used for the verification exercise.

³ <https://salome-platform.org/>

Figure 3.5 MegaRoller model in Code_Aster – mesh size 0.5m x 0.5m

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Preliminary Mesh Sensitivity Study

In this section, the effects of mesh density on the maximum deflection are investigated in both SAP2000 and Code_Aster, using four different resolutions.

Choosing an appropriate mesh density is extremely important in any FE analysis task. If the mesh size is too coarse, the elements may not be able to accurately represent the response of the structure, potentially leading to errors in the results of the analysis that are often unconservative. Conversely, if the mesh is too fine, the simulation may require excessive computer resources and lead to excessively long run times. The run time aspect is particularly important in the case of the MegaRoller model, as the FE model forms part of a coupled hydro-elastic loads tool and must be solved at every time step during loads simulations. In order to find a balance between accuracy and computational time, the sensitivity of the structural response to the mesh density was investigated in a preliminary exercise, using Load Case 1.

To refine the mesh density in SAP2000, the '*Automatic Area Mesh*' option was applied to the elements of the medium mesh (1.5m x 1.67m), where the program automatically generates the desired mesh density and applies the distributed loads at the appropriate nodes during the analysis. Similarly, the Code_Aster model used an in-house Python script to automate the application of nodal forces to a given mesh.

For each mesh size, the deflection of the flap was output by the FE model. Table 3.2 and Table 3.3 show the maximum deflection for the different mesh size, along with the percentage of error compared to the finest mesh (0.25m x 0.25m) for SAP2000 and Code_Aster, respectively. The computational time for SAP2000 is also shown to illustrate the increase in required computational resources as the mesh is refined.

Table 3.2 Results of the mesh density investigation in SAP2000

Mesh size [m]	Maximum deflection (m)	Error [%]	Computational time [min]
3.00 x 1.67	0.03294	5.9%	6.2
1.50 x 1.67	0.03429	2.0%	12.9
0.50 x 0.50	0.03494	0.2%	59.6
0.25 x 0.25	0.03500	N/A	83.3

Table 3.3 Results of the mesh density investigation in Code_Aster

Mesh size [m]	Maximum deflection (m)	Error [%]
3.00 x 1.67	0.0322	9.8%
1.50 x 1.67	0.0338	5.3%
0.50 x 0.50	0.0341	4.5%
0.25 x 0.25	0.0357	N/A

Figure 3.6 shows that, for both FE models considered, the maximum deflection converges towards c.0.035m as the element size is reduced. However, using sizes smaller than 1.5m is shown to give less benefit, with the maximum deflection in SAP2000 changing by less than 1% but the computational time increasing by up to 6-folds. In Code_Aster, very small element sizes relative to the overall flap dimensions were seen to be more unstable. This is possibly due to the shell element assumptions no longer being valid (i.e., element thickness is close to the length and width) and indicates a solid model would be better suited for very high-fidelity analysis.

Figure 3.6 Distribution of the maximum deflection of the flap (m) with the mesh density (m): SAP2000 (in red) and Code_Aster (in blue)

In general, the two FE models present a similar sensitivity to mesh size. Overall, element sizes below approximately 1.5m appear to result in a converged solution for both solvers, with an error in the maximum deflection of less than 1% compared to the results from the finest mesh. Considering the increase in the computational time required as element size is reduced, and in an initial attempt to balance the need for accuracy with computational efficiency, a 0.5m x 0.5m mesh was selected to be used in both FE solvers for the rest of the verification study.

3.2.2 Static Analysis – Load Case 1

In this section the Load Case 1 outputs of the SAP2000 and Code_Aster FE models are compared in terms of flap deformation.

Figure 3.7 shows the deformation in surge (Ux) direction, output by SAP2000 (in red) and Code_Aster (in blue) at joint no. 1042, located at the center of upper edge (indicated by a blue point in Figure 3.8). Overall, the two solvers exhibit a very similar displacement output. The deformed shape is shown in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.7 Time-series of deformation in surge (m) at mid-point of the upper edge (joint 1042): SAP2000 (in red) and Code_Aster (in blue)

Figure 3.8 Deformation of the flap at t=414s (amplified by a factor of 100): blue point is joint 1042, green point is joint 1077 and red point is joint 1007.

Table 3.4 to Table 3.6 compare the results between the displacement in surge from the two FE solvers for three example locations on the flap: left corner, centre and right corner of the upper edge (shown in green, blue and red, respectively, in Figure 3.8). Overall, the minimum and maximum deflections output by both solvers are very similar, with a maximum difference of less than 3.5% (for the maximum deflection at joint 1077). It can also be seen that the flap deflects symmetrically, as expected due to the symmetrical load.

Table 3.4 Comparison of the peak displacements, at the center of upper edge (joint 1042)

Joint 1042	Minimum (mm)	Maximum (mm)
SAP2000	-24.7	34.9
Code_Aster	-24.1	34.1

Table 3.5 Comparison of the peak displacements, at the left corner of upper edge (joint 1077)

Joint 1077	Minimum (mm)	Maximum (mm)
SAP2000	-14.3	21.0
Code_Aster	-13.8	20.3

Table 3.6 Comparison of the peak displacements, at the right corner of upper edge (joint 1007)

Joint 1007	Minimum (mm)	Maximum (mm)
SAP2000	-14.3	20.9
Code_Aster	-13.9	20.3

According to the SAP2000 results, the maximum deflection is 34.9mm at 414th time step and occurs at the centre of the flap (joint 1042). The corresponding result from the Code_Aster is 34.1mm, a difference of 2.3%.

3.2.3 Static Analysis – Load Case 2

In this section the Load Case 2 outputs from the SAP2000 and Code_Aster FE models are compared in terms of flap deformation. For this load case, both normal (X) and transverse (Y) forces were applied to the structural models as nodal forces.

Figure 3.10 shows the deformation in surge (U_x) and in sway (U_y) directions, output by SAP2000 (in red) and Code_Aster (in blue) at joint no. 1042. Overall, the two solvers exhibit a very similar displacement output. The deformed shape is shown in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.9 Time-series of deformation in surge (m) at mid-point of the upper edge (joint 1042): SAP2000(in red) and Code_Aster (in blue)

Figure 3.10 Deformation of the flap at the time of peak displacement, 414th time step. (amplified by a factor of 100): blue point is joint 1042, green point is joint 1077 and red point is joint 1007.

Table 3.7 to Table 3.9 compare both the surge (U_x) and sway (U_y) deformation of the flap between the two FE solvers for three example locations on the flap: left corner, centre and right corner of the upper edge (shown in green, blue and red, respectively, in Figure 3.10). Overall, the minimum and maximum deflections output by both solvers are very similar, with a maximum difference of about 5% (for the maximum deflection in sway at joint 1042). It can also be seen that the flap deflects asymmetrically, as expected due to the asymmetrical load.

Table 3.7 Comparison of the peak displacements, at the center of upper edge (joint 1042)

Joint 1042	Ux (mm)		Uy (mm)	
	Min	Max	Min	Max
SAP2000	-25.4	26.5	-0.19	0.22
Code_Aster	-24.7	25.8	-0.20	0.23

Table 3.8 Comparison of the peak displacements, at the left corner of upper edge (joint 1077)

Joint 1077	Ux (mm)		Uy (mm)	
	Min	Max	Min	Max
SAP2000	-15.6	16.7	-1.3	1.1
Code_Aster	-15.1	16.2	-1.3	1.1

Table 3.9 Comparison of the peak displacements, at the right corner of upper edge (joint 1007)

Joint 1007	Ux (mm)		Uy (mm)	
	Min	Max	Min	Max
SAP2000	-14.7	15.3	-1.0	1.3
Code_Aster	-14.2	14.8	-1.0	1.3

This close agreement provides confidence in the modelling approach and suggests that the shell elements used in the Code_Aster FE solver are capable of handling transverse (i.e., U_y) loads as well as the normal forces.

3.3 Conclusions and Recommendations

This task aimed to provide initial verification of the structural model of the MegaRoller device developed in Code_Aster. A similar FE model of the MegaRoller flap was built in the FE solver SAP2000, and two static case studies were considered to compare the flap deflections output from both models.

In a FE analysis, finding the correct mesh density is, among other variables, one of the significant parameters to control the accuracy of the results. Typically, a high-density mesh means more accurate results. However, this must be balanced against the available computational resources. In a preliminary step to the verification exercise, the effects of different mesh sizes on the simulation results were investigated. Maximum deflections of the flap were shown to converge as element size was reduced, with similar convergence patterns featured by both FE solvers. A mesh size of 0.5m x 0.5m was chosen as an initial balance between accuracy and computational requirements.

The deformation of the flap estimated by the two FE models was then compared for two static load cases, varying the wave angle. Deformation time-series and deformation maxima at three example points across the width of the flap showed close agreement between the two FE models. Overall, these results provide confidence in the FE model used as part of the WP1.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This document constitutes a verification and validation report for the MegaRoller WEC numerical model developed under WP1, describing the approach and the results of the comparison of the numerical model with already validated tools and experimental measurements. The numerical models were developed in a custom version of the numerical simulation package WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) and was documented in [D1.1, 2018] and [D1.2, 2019].

In [D1.1, 2018], a preliminary validation of the model was conducted using data from small-scale models which were tested in a wave tank at Queen's University in Belfast, UK. The present document builds on this preliminary validation exercise using real sea measurement data from the WaveRoller demonstration unit deployed at the Peniche site (Portugal). The following high-level conclusions can be drawn from the loads model validation exercise and sensitivity studies presented in this report:

- The PTO torque is relatively insensitive to the viscous drag formulation, PTO force cap and consideration of non-linear effects. This is likely due to the low wave heights simulated and therefore lower forces and velocities.
- The inclusion of wave spreading generally reduces the simulated PTO torque. In some sea states, the WEC-Sim results change from over-predicting the measured data to under-predicting it, although the overall effect on the overall percentage difference is relatively small.
- The inclusion of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients generally increases the predicted PTO torque. This is consistent with the findings of the initial MegaRoller loads modelling [D1.2, 2019].
- The inclusion of a database of hydrodynamic coefficients allows the prediction of non-zero mean flap angles, although the predicted mean angles are still significantly lower than the measured data provided, with the simulation generally under-estimating the mean by an average of 67%.
- The updated model, including spread waves and a database of hydrodynamic coefficients, results in a slightly more accurate representation of the measured data, although the difference in overall percentage difference between WEC-Sim and the measured data is small.

More generally, this work suggests that, even for normal operating conditions and relatively benign sea states, WEC-Sim is capable of predicting RMS values of key metrics to within approximately 20%. Differences for extreme events and when considering maximum values are likely to increase, potentially significantly so. For concept design studies, such as MegaRoller, this level of accuracy may be acceptable, especially considering the load factors typically applied which are intended in part to compensate for this uncertainty. However, for detailed design and in-depth optimisation studies, it is likely that further development of these tools would be required (e.g. by calibrating against tank test data or CFD simulations).

In a second exercise, the structural model developed under WP1 was verified by comparing outputs from Code_Aster with a separate finite-element tool. A similar FE model of the MegaRoller flap was built in the FE solver SAP2000, and two static case studies were considered to compare the flap deflections output from both models.

In a FE analysis, finding the correct mesh density is, among other variables, one of the significant parameters to control the accuracy of the results. Typically, a high-density mesh means more accurate results. However, this must be balanced against the available computational resources. In a preliminary step to the verification exercise, the effects of different mesh sizes on the simulation results were investigated. Maximum deflections of the flap were shown to converge as element size was reduced, with similar convergence patterns featured by both FE solvers. A mesh size of 0.5m x 0.5m was chosen as an initial balance between accuracy and computational requirements.

The deformation of the flap estimated by the two FE models was then compared for two static load cases, varying the wave angle. Deformation time-series and deformation maxima at three example points across the width of the flap showed close agreement between the two FE models. Overall, these results provide confidence in the FE model used as part of the WP1.

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